

LEADING THE SCHOOL DURING AND AFTER THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC: THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF SCHOOL HEADS

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ABSTRACT

This study made further analysis to find out how school leaders continue despite the challenges they face. This also gives leaders a deeper grasp on how to manage schools during times of crisis. To attain it, the lived experiences of the school heads during and after the COVID-19 pandemic were investigated. Using a qualitative descriptive method, nine school heads of the Schools Division of Caloocan, North I District based on pre-determined criteria. The findings revealed that the school heads became situational leaders during the pandemic, while adaptive leaders after the pandemic. The most challenging issue encountered was student learning and assessment. The changes they had in terms of leadership were that they became open-minded and committed. Meanwhile, they learned that as school heads during the pandemic, resilience was key. With the results, the following are suggested for the school heads to undergo: development and implementation of a Leadership Enhancement Program that focuses on empowerment; workshops and seminars to help learn and maximize the use of Information and Communication Technology in managing and supervising the school and the administrative and teaching staff; utilize the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) session to converse and share different teaching strategies and to come up with an assessment matrix to properly align the content standards, learning competencies, and classroom activities and evaluations; conduct of a leadership assessment to determine how to improve the leadership; and investigate further the complexity of leadership roles

during post-pandemic, the impact of external and internal factors that influenced leadership styles.

Keywords: *Educational Management, leadership, leaders, pandemic, resiliency, school heads*

INTRODUCTION

Even before the pandemic, school leaders had already encountered challenges in fulfilling their roles. Their roles were supervising, checking learning plans, conducting research, implementing policies, supporting and training teachers, and enhancing themselves further through leadership training and further studies (Jambangan, 2024). However, as the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted education across the globe, school leaders faced more challenges. Schools were forced to implement remote learning and limited in-person work arrangements guided by the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) (DepEd Order No. 12, s. 2020). This sudden change created obstacles for schools and leaders to continue teaching and learning amidst the pandemic. Hence, BE-LCP was designed to address the challenges in basic education caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (Abril & Callo, 2021).

Moreover, in the global scenario, Bradbury et al. (2022) state that learners' basic knowledge needs should be prioritized despite adversity. Considering this statement, the teachers and the school heads were highly significant in leading the school despite the pandemic.

However, several factors hindered the school leaders from adapting to environmental changes (Maca, 2023). These were the absence of interpersonal relationships; contact between students and teachers, parents, school management, and the community (Constantia et al., 2021). Consequently, the emotional, organizational, and professional roles of the school heads were at risk (Sezer & Uzun, 2020).

Meanwhile, to cope with the adversities experienced, Nargil (2024) mentioned several things that school heads should consider in improving their leadership skills. These were navigating leadership, developing crisis management skills, addressing reliance on technology, reevaluating traditional standards, promoting inclusivity in remote learning, and prioritizing essential needs. By examining the school heads' changes and perspectives in their roles during the pandemic, it aimed to discover the approaches they had implemented upon confronting the challenges they had faced. Consequently, there were limited studies that would exhibit the lessons learned and coping mechanisms these leaders employed during the pandemic.

This study implied that further analysis was required to find out how school leaders continue despite the challenges they face. Also, this would be significant as it gave leaders a deeper grasp on how to manage schools during times of crisis. Hence, the purpose of this research was to also seek further recommendations for improvements for

the school heads, teachers, learners, parents, and other stakeholders, as well as the Department of Education through the different divisions and clusters, especially when hard times occur.

Research Questions

1. How do the school heads describe the changes in their leadership roles during and after the COVID-19 pandemic?
2. What were their perspectives regarding the alterations in their leadership roles as the pandemic unfolded?
3. What challenges have they encountered in their leadership roles during the pandemic?
4. What subsequent changes have they experienced in their leadership approaches after confronting the challenges?
5. What lessons have they learned regarding their experiences in leading schools during the pandemic?

METHODOLOGY

The research is designed using a qualitative descriptive approach. The qualitative description provides a comprehensive grasp of certain events. This approach can be used in several ways, such as a standalone research design, as a forerunner to more extensive qualitative studies, and most frequently as the qualitative component in mixed-methods studies. Although descriptive techniques are often used, there must be more methodological advice regarding this design in books or articles. Because these approaches are not adequately represented in research texts, inexperienced researchers have occasionally used grounded theory or phenomenology without adhering to their requirements or having a sound justification (Doyle et al., 2020).

The study's data collection involved interviews (in-depth questioning) and gathering related literature and studies on the lived experiences of the school heads during and after the pandemic. The key sources of data for the study, on which the researcher extensively relied, were the transcriptions of the interviews with the nine school heads from the Schools Division of Caloocan City, North I District. The school heads were chosen based on the following criteria: (the school head has been in the position for at least five years before the pandemic, with varying characteristics in terms of age and leadership experience).

Meanwhile, a secondary source was a key informant, a Public School District Supervisor, and all studies and publications that have been evaluated in connection with the claim made by the study.

The recorded interviews were transcribed, and the researcher identified categories based on the transcripts. These categories were analyzed and grouped into codes and themes and were later summarized, analyzed, and interpreted.

To ensure the research instrument's validity and reliability, a thorough validation was undertaken. The first version of the interview guide with six questions was validated by the three experts comprised of a School Head, a Master teacher, and a District Supervisor. Their role was to assess the interview guide for relevance, clarity, and alignment with the study's purposes.

These experts provided valuable feedback on the interview guide, identifying potential areas for improvement and suggesting modifications to ensure that the questions were clear, comprehensive, and conducive to gathering meaningful data. By incorporating their recommendations, the researcher was able to enhance the instrument's overall quality, ensuring that it was well-suited to the study's aims.

The first process of the study was that the researcher submitted an official letter of authorization to the Schools Division Superintendent at the Caloocan City Schools Division Office to proceed with the study. The Office of the Schools Division Superintendent approved and issued an endorsement letter, allowing the researcher to conduct interviews with the school heads.

Upon approval, the researcher went to the nine school heads and sought their consent for individual interviews. The researcher set an appointment for the school heads' one-on-one interviews that were conducted in a private setting that is conducive to open discussion and at their most convenient time, ensuring that there are no disturbances, taking into consideration their availability and other commitments. The researcher informed the participants that their interviews would be recorded (audio and/or video) and a verbatim transcription would be done afterward.

The subsequent phase of the research will involve meticulously conducted individual interviews with each participant. During these interviews, the researcher posed a series of thought-provoking inquiries related to the participants' initial perceptions and evaluations of proficiency improvement strategies. These interviews served as a crucial methodological approach to acquire essential data, insights, and perspectives from the participants. The aim was to gain a profound understanding of the lived experiences of school heads during disruptive times.

According to Ruslin et al. (2022) a research interview is a sophisticated and intricate process involving a verbal exchange between two individuals with the primary objective of acquiring pertinent and valuable data for a comprehensive investigation. This methodological approach is employed within academic research to systematically collect information, enabling researchers to delve deeper into the subject matter and gain a more profound understanding of the phenomenon under scrutiny.

The final step of this research involved the analysis of the gathered data using thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is a method for analyzing qualitative data that involves identifying similarities in the meaning of the data to pinpoint themes. This process requires the researcher's expertise in actively and reflectively making sense of the data.

The finalized interview guide, which reflects the cumulative feedback from the expert validation, was ready for use in the data collection process. It has been designed to facilitate meaningful dialogue with the school heads, providing a structured yet flexible framework for gathering rich qualitative data. The final version of the interview guide can be found in the Appendices section of the research document, serving as a key tool for the study's success.

This study focused on the lived experiences of school heads during the COVID-19 Pandemic in 2020 to Post-Pandemic in 2023. The school heads' experiences were from the data collected through the in-depth interviews and did not represent the overall experiences of school heads, but only within the municipality of Caloocan. The selected nine school heads were from the Schools Division of Caloocan, North I District, who had been in the position for at least five years before the pandemic, with varying characteristics in terms of age, gender, and leadership experiences. The participants were selected using Criterion sampling.

RESULTS

Changes in the leadership roles of school heads during and after the pandemic

Situational Leadership

It was known in the field of managerial leadership theories that let leaders apply leading styles according to their subordinates' maturity level.

In this study, the school heads claimed that they had changed their leadership style during the pandemic. As stated by School Head B:

“So, my leadership style is situational. It's according to the need of the situation.”- School Head B

Moreover, situational leaders employ strategies according to the needs of the moment and help in developing new techniques that suit the situation. This case is supported by School Head I, who stated:

“During the pandemic, my leadership evolved significantly to adapt to the unprecedented circumstances.”- School Head I

Remote Leadership

School heads had no choice but to supervise their teachers remotely. Because of the health restrictions and lockdowns, schools are forced to close and adapt their work-from-home arrangements. School Heads D, E, and F share:

A new landscape of educational system. Hindi lang naman sa Pilipinas kundi sa buong mundo. Nagkikita lang kayo online.[It is not only in the Philippines but worldwide. We see each other online]- School Head D

Then here, during the pandemic, it's very difficult. Very difficult, and on my part, very challenging. Since I was not able to meet. Yes. The parents, the stakeholders, and the teachers as well. I only met the office staff. - School Head E

...there was a significant shift to remote leadership, necessitating a greater emphasis on virtual communication, adaptability, and supporting team well-being.- School Head F

In the case of School Head E, he has experienced difficulties, especially because he was not able to meet the parents and other stakeholders face-to-face. In response, School Head F shares how significant virtual communication was during those adverse times.

Supporting and Motivating Team

Due to the challenges they faced during the implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) (Dep.Ed. order no. 12, s. 2020). The school heads do their best to be positive despite the hardships they face. Their positive outlook, support, and motivation are crucial as they dealt with teachers who were also feeling lost and anxious. According to School Heads A, F, G, and H:

...leadership is all about inspiring your people, motivating them so that they will collaborate with you on whatever your plans are in the school. It's more about inspiring them. -School Head A

The experience prompted me to refine my digital leadership skills, fostering resilience and flexibility in both myself and my team.- School Head F

Successful leadership during the pandemic required resilience, empathy, and the ability to adapt quickly to new circumstances while remaining focused on the well-being and success of students and staff.- School Head G

I have become more understanding and empathetic in dealing with setbacks and distractions. - School Head H

They also cited the three main practices these school heads employed: strength-based practices, values-based practices, and needs-based practices. All are connected to the leadership practices known as situational leadership.

The claims of the school head prove that despite the limitations in communication, they are still able to supervise remotely and to make sure that even with limited resources, especially in terms of communication, they maximized the use of online/virtual to reach those students and other stakeholders. This is supported by the claim of the school division superintendent, who says:

“School heads had to quickly adapt to changing circumstances, implementing emergency plans, and shifting to remote learning. This required flexibility and rapid decision-making skills.”- PSDS

Adaptive Leader

After the outbreak of the pandemic, the school heads admitted several changes in the way they led the school. Being a situational leader, they become adaptive to all the changes that happen. Since their approach would depend on the different situations, they become resilient, creative, and resourceful. It has also strengthened their flexibility and community relationships as they fostered a more flexible educational environment. These are attested by School Heads A, B, C, D, E, H, and I who state:

“ I became adaptive to change.”- School Head A

“the shift of how you transform your leadership role and practices depends on the situation.” -School Head B

“We are resilient. We are creative, and resourceful.” -School Head C

“I maintained educational demands, focus on continuous learning and adapting leadership practices.” - School Head D

“I Strengthened democratic leadership, emphasized flexibility and community-building.”- School Head E

“I demonstrated empathy, understanding, and adaptability in leadership.” - School Head H

“...embracing the positive changes, like the integration of technology in everyday learning and fostering a more flexible and resilient educational environment. - Head I

Technologically Driven Leader

The capability of the school heads to embrace technology and explore new approaches with the aid of virtual learning environments. They have also integrated technology into addressing problems like health restrictions as they utilized digital equipment to communicate with teachers, students, and other stakeholders. These are attested by School Heads F, G, and I, as they claim:

“I Focused on employee well-being, embraced technology, and maintained effective remote work policies.”- School Head F

“The pandemic spurred innovation in teaching and learning practices, with educators exploring new approaches to engage students in virtual and hybrid learning environments”- School Head G

“...embracing the positive changes, like the integration of technology in everyday learning and fostering a more flexible and resilient educational environment.” - School Head I

Empathic Leader

Shows how school heads became concerned for their teachers' well-being. They also demonstrate understanding and adaptability, while trying their best to address the mental health issues encountered not only by teachers but also by students. These are shared by School Heads F, H, and I as they share:

“I Focused on employee well-being”- School Head F

“I demonstrated empathy, understanding, and adaptability...” - School Head H

“the role has shifted towards addressing the long-term impacts of the crisis, such as learning loss and mental health issues, while also embracing the positive changes..”- School Head I

School Head I added:

“...fostering a more flexible and resilient educational environment.” - School Head I

From the three initial codes, the researcher assigned the theme “The school head as an adaptive leader after the pandemic” to describe the changes in the leadership roles and practices of school heads after the pandemic.

In this situation, the school heads realize how their leadership styles were enhanced, restructured, and improved emotionally. The PSDS remarks:

“Many school heads experienced personal growth and developed new perspectives on leadership. The challenges of the pandemic tested their resilience and often led to a deeper understanding of their role and its impact.”- PSDS

Since schools are situated in different contexts and environments, the experiences of the school heads vary, which makes them more empathic and adaptable. PSDS further says:

“These experiences varied widely depending on the local context, available resources, and specific challenges faced by each institution. However, the pandemic universally underscored the importance of strong, adaptable, and empathetic leadership in education.”- PSDS

Perspectives of school heads regarding the Alterations in their leadership roles as the pandemic unfolded

Adaptation to technology, communication and modalities

It is the biggest alteration in the task of school heads when the pandemic came. They are forced to adapt technology not only as a means of teaching but also in communication. Since the teaching modality has changed, no new strategies and methods are utilized, which concerns not only teachers but also the school heads. Having a different working set-up, they are more concerned with the transparency and frequency of communication. All of which pose challenges and cause alterations to leadership roles. These are exemplified by School Heads A, C, E, H, and I, as they share:

“...the main issue here is how am I going to communicate the plans, and the goals clearly doon sa aking mga teachers or stakeholders [the goals clearly were toward my teachers or stakeholders] ... We took advantage of the use of the technology.” - School Head A
“..Teaching strategies and activities that must be presented and must be achieved even if there is an ongoing pandemic.” - School Head C

“There were the modular and online classes. Well, it changed. That's why you have to monitor. You have to monitor the staff, the teachers, as well as the learners.” - School Head E

“It was more exciting in the past because the shift in technology was a brand-new experience for teachers and everyone.”- School Head H

New school set-up

Again, caused by distance learning, presents school supervision with challenges and uncertainties. Since everyone relied on the Internet as a means of communication, the school heads are also hesitant as to how it would be managed, just as they were during face-to-face learning. School Heads B and C share:

“There are so many uncertainties during the onset of the pandemic. So, you have to learn what kind of education setup are you going to use during the pandemic.”-School Head B

“...alterations are not only in the way you manage your school but also in the offering of the teaching strategies and activities” - School Head C

Alterations of ways to supervise

Was made due to different situations encountered; however, despite the different ways of teaching and supervising, the school heads claim that there is no difference in terms of being the leader, the only difference is that they needed to find feasible ways to perform them. School Heads D and E share:

“Actually, yung leadership role naman ng principal hindi naman totally nabago. Kaya lang ang naging problema nga kasi, yung supervisory and managerial na task ng school head as a leader... [The leadership role as principal was not totally changed. However, it was a challenge since the main task was to supervise and manage as a leader...]- School Head D

School Head D mentions that only the modality is changed and not the role as the leaders. However, it is further stated:

“Ang nagbago lang sa supervision ng teachers kung paano sila magturo. Hindi ka na pupunta sa classroom, nasa online lang. Kaya nga ang

problema doon hindi mo rin nakikita how effective the teachers are. [What changed was the way teachers perform their jobs. You are not anymore going inside the classroom since it's online. The challenge was you can't see how effective the teachers were] - School Head D

It is clear that he is not sure how to assess the effectiveness of the teacher with the online modality.

The onset, of course, there are some programs presented by the DepEd, as well as the Division of Calocan. And you know, ma'am, that there were the modular and online classes. - School Head E

Adaptation to new nature of work

Makes the school heads turn to being agile and discover more about themselves as leaders. They have seen how their perspectives and approaches have evolved amidst the complex situation. School Heads F and G share:

“At the start of the pandemic, I initially saw challenges in adapting to remote work but quickly recognized the need for agile leadership.” - School Head F

“learning in their leadership roles, continually evolving their perspectives and approaches to effectively navigate the complexities of the situation.” - School Head G

Setting of a new mindset and leadership style

Encompasses the school head being flexible, resilient, a team leader, a communicator, keen on adaptation, empathic, and open-minded. Because of the alterations to their roles as leaders, they also open themselves up to a new mindset of leadership. According to School Heads F, G, and I:

“As the pandemic unfolded, my perspective evolved to prioritize empathy, flexibility, and digital communication, fostering a more resilient and cohesive team. - School Head F

“As the pandemic unfolded, principals likely underwent a process of adaptation, growth, and learning...” School Head G

“I realized that traditional leadership approaches needed to be re-evaluated. There was an urgent need for a more empathetic and communicative leader...It was crucial to be adaptable, open to new ideas, and ready to make quick decisions. I also recognized the importance of collaboration and teamwork...”- School Head I

From the five initial codes, the researcher assigns the theme “The school heads adaptation to technology, communication, and new modalities” to describe the perspectives of school heads regarding the alterations in their leadership roles as the pandemic unfolded.

Despite the challenges faced, the school heads still manage to address them. As confirmed by the SDS:

“Transitioning to online learning platforms posed significant technological challenges. School heads had to ensure that both teachers and students had access to necessary resources and training to facilitate effective online education.”- SDS

Based on the statement of the school division superintendent, the school heads still had to ensure that the resources needed to facilitate online learning were available. Thus, the excerpts presented were manifestations of the school heads' positive response to the situation.

Challenges that the school heads encountered in their leadership roles during the pandemic

Navigating Unclear communication channels

It is obvious not only in school but around the globe. The main problem found in terms of communication is to establish collaboration between the school and the parents as partners in the students' learning process since they are just staying at home. during the pandemic, communication was one of the several issues faced by schools. According to School Heads A, B, E, F, G, and H:

“One of the significant challenges that I encountered in my leadership is more on how am I going to communicate with my teachers and of course with the parents.”- School Head A

“the challenge there was not only the connectivity but also the teachers the students.”- School Head B

“I had to build a strong connection with the stakeholders, not only the stakeholders but the teachers and the people in the school, the staff, and everybody here in the school.”- School Head E

“ensuring effective remote communication, and addressing individual well-being concerns... implementing regular virtual check-ins, promoting open communication channels...” -School Head F

“worked to secure technology resources for students who lacked access at home and implemented strategies to monitor and support student engagement and progress in virtual classrooms..” – School Head G

Communication has played a crucial role in those times to ensure that the students are also doing their tasks at home. However, the internet connection is a big hindrance. School Head I further state:

“it is the slow and unreliable internet connection that happens efficient monitoring and timely communications”-School Head I

Managing Public Health Restrictions

It is caused by the COVID-19 Pandemic. Aside from distance learning, social distancing was also observed. This has also caused leaders to overcome fear and ensure the safety of the teachers and staff, including themselves.

DepEd Order no. 14 s. In 2020, the Guidelines on the Required Health Standards in Basic Education Offices and Schools were issued, which enumerated the Specific measures for COVID-19 prevention and Mitigation in Schools. The school heads had to follow these provisions while finding ways to continue the teaching and learning process amidst the crisis. School Head C shares:

“During the COVID-19 pandemic, of course, the most significant challenges were, the challenges that a leader has experienced, like me to overcome your fear because COVID-19 is life-threatening, isn't it? Yes. So, you have to be prepared to face the reality that when you do your work you should be extra careful and you should protect also yourself, like protect yourself. You should be protecting other people while you are doing your task. So, that is the most challenging. So, what I did was pray and follow the advice of the experts and medical experts not to expose ourselves to the danger but of course, as a leader of the institution you are always exposed.”- School Head C

To support this claim, the school division superintendent says:

“Navigating constantly changing government regulations and health guidelines was a key part of school leaders' roles. They had to ensure that their schools complied with health and safety protocols to protect their communities” -SDS

School head C admits that no matter how careful he was to not be exposed to the virus, he could not assure it since he was the school head and had to face people and go to places or offices to represent the institution; hence, they needed to be the frontline of the school.

Challenges in learning and assessment result reliability

This has something to do with the communication between the teachers and students. Since teachers conducted online classes, it was a big challenge to assist teachers on how they would maintain academic standards. To add to that, not all students can join the online classes, which resulted in the use of modules. However, it was not also ensured if the answers to the modules were done by the students themselves. This is proclaimed by School Heads A, B, D, and I, and they say:

“how are we going to collaborate in order to effectively conduct classes through online..”- School Head A

“The biggest challenge is how to deliver the learning process, to maintain the academic standard of education.” – School Head B

“Maraming mga bata ang hindi pumapasok kasi wala silang pang-online. Tapos yung sa mga modules, hindi mo alam kung sila talaga ang sumasagot. Hindi natin na-assess kung talaga bang natuto sila.[Many students cannot join the online class. The modules, we were not sure if they were the one who answered them. We cannot assess if the students learned.]”-School Head D

“The most significant challenges included ensuring the continuity of education..”- School Head I

Another challenges that the school head encountered are the learning plans, access to resources, instructional practices for remote learning, technology resources, and the new modality itself. These are shared by School Head G who proclaims:

“One of the primary challenges was ensuring continuity of learning for students amidst school closures and transitions to remote or hybrid learning models. This required principals to coordinate with teachers to develop and implement effective remote learning plans, ensuring equitable access to resources and support for all students...The pandemic placed significant stress on educators, who had to adapt quickly to new modalities while also managing their own personal and family challenges.”- School Head G

Mental health and morale

As school heads saw how important addressing individual concerns, providing support, showing empathy, motivating, engaging, and prioritizing mental health, on top of other things. Mazrekaj and De Witte (2023) report how the length of school closures resulted in learners' deficits in learning and deterioration in mental health. Being school heads, the principals express themselves on how they dealt with the challenges, especially on mental health. School Heads B, F, and I share:

“...the challenge there was not only the connectivity but also the teachers the students...”- School Head B

School Head B mentions that he had problems on both students and teachers, especially during time when he could not reach them virtually to check what was happening.

“The most significant challenges during the pandemic were maintaining team morale, ensuring effective remote communication, and addressing individual well-being concerns...regular virtual check-ins, promoting open communication channels, and providing resources for mental health support.”- School Head F

“We invested in technology and provided extensive training for teachers, established robust support systems for students and parents, and prioritized mental health by offering access to counselors and regular check-ins.- School Head I

This is supported by the claim of the school division superintendent who says:

“The pandemic significantly impacted the emotional and mental well-being of school leaders. They often had to manage their own stress while supporting the mental health of their staff and students.”- PSDS

From the four initial codes, the researcher assigns the theme “The school heads challenges in learning and assessment” to describe the challenges that the school heads encountered in their leadership roles during the pandemic.

As supported by the school division superintendent, it is stressed that:

“Transitioning to online learning platforms posed significant technological challenges. School heads had to ensure that both teachers and students had access to necessary resources and training to facilitate effective online education.”- PSDS

Subsequent changes that the school heads experienced in their leadership approaches after confronting the challenges brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic

Resiliency and proactivity

It is about the school head’s change in how he handled situations positively. They have learned to listen, be appreciative, and show concern for teachers’ and students’ well-being. This is claimed by School Heads A, C, F, and I, as they share:

“...you become more resilient and compassionate. Because you become more understanding of your people.” - School Head A

He further adds:

“parang naging less reactive ako sa sitwasyon. Kasi hindi lahat ng bagay is kailangan mag-react. Ang kailangan lang siguro ngayon is, mas matuto kang makinig.[I became less reactive to situations. Not all things should be taken heavily. What we need is to learn and to listen.] - School Head A

“You must be more innovative, more creative and more positive in a way that you should look into the things that have possibilities to lessen the problem and not to add to the problem...this pandemic improved me because I learned how to appreciate more the gifts of God and the freedom to work without any threat.” - School head C

“my leadership approaches evolved to prioritize flexibility, resilience, and a heightened focus on employee well-being.”- School Head F

“My leadership practices have become more inclusive and collaborative...offer flexibility and prioritize the mental and emotional well-being of students and staff.” -School Head I

Adaptive and flexible

It is another leadership quality that the school heads developed after the COVID-19 pandemic. They have described themselves as diverse and situational leaders. They prioritize flexibility and adaptability. These are cited by School Heads B, F, G, and I as they share:

“you have to be a situational leader. Whatever the situation is that you are in right now, you can't stick to your leadership style. You have to be a diverse leader because it depends on the situation.”

School Head B

“...my leadership approaches evolved to prioritize flexibility...I cultivated a greater appreciation for adaptability and the importance of supporting the holistic needs of my team.” - School head F

“I have recognized the importance of flexibility and adaptability in leadership..” School Head G

“offer flexibility and prioritize the mental and emotional well-being of students and staff.”- School Head I

This is also supported by the school division superintendent, who remarked:

“School heads had to quickly adapt to changing circumstances, implementing emergency plans, and shifting to remote learning. This required flexibility and rapid decision-making skills.”- PSDS

Open and committed

The school heads describe themselves as resourceful, creative, innovative, and open to change. They have also mentioned that they become transformative leaders. They have considered themselves servants who were more clear and transparent in terms of communication as they became more understanding and empathic. They have become more adept at the virtual environment as they embrace the changes and innovations. Moreover, they have seen the importance of strengthening partnerships with stakeholders and being collaborative. School leaders C, D, E, F, G, H, and I share:

“to intensify and be determined to use these qualities to overcome the challenges... to intensify and be determined to use these qualities to overcome the challenges” - School Head C

“ako ay servant leader, yun ang ginagawa ko and even transformational leadership. ...dapat open ka sa pagbabago

...kailangan mong mag-adapt sa panahon. [I am a servant leader, I am a transformational leader.. I have to be open to changes. I have to adapt to the current situation]

“My kind of leadership became strong. I just intensified being a democratic leader. I have to be flexible and resourceful enough.” - School Head E

“my leadership approaches evolved to prioritize flexibility..I cultivated a greater appreciation for adaptability” School Head F

“I have recognized the importance of flexibility and adaptability in leadership.”- School Head G

“offer flexibility” - School Head I

These different claims support the emergence of the theme in this portion of the study - the open-mindedness and commitment.

From the three initial codes, the researcher has assigned the theme “The school heads open-mindedness and commitment” to describe subsequent changes that the school heads experienced in their leadership approaches and practices after the COVID-19 Pandemic.

Lessons learned from the experiences of school heads in leading schools during the pandemic

Resiliency

This represents the lessons learned by the school heads while leading the school amidst the pandemic. They claim that they learned how to always be prepared, always have a plan, and be open-minded, resilient, flexible, adaptable, compassionate, creative, and determined. These are exemplified by School Heads B, C, E, F, G, and I, as they share:

“be open-minded. You have to be ready for the changes that are happening” - School Head B

“always be prepared for what will happen because nothing is permanent. You should always have a plan to have these things be faced with strength in proper positive ways or means that all the challenges.” - School C

“we have to be resilient. No matter what happens, we have to be resilient.”- School Head E

“the pandemic has taught me the enduring importance of flexibility, adaptability...the value of resilience and the need to continuously evolve in response to dynamic circumstances, shaping a more resilient and future-ready leadership approach.”- School Head F

“prioritizing resilience, well-being...community-building, and distributed leadership, I am confident in my ability to lead my

institution through future challenges and uncertainties with compassion, creativity, and determination.” - School Head G
“The pandemic taught me the importance of adaptability, resilience...I will focus on being prepared for change, building a resilient school community.” -School Head I

Being resilient means being ready for whatever challenges came along the way. The school head shares noteworthy learning experiences they had during the pandemic. As also cited by the school division superintendent:

“As the immediate crisis abated, school leaders focused on long-term recovery plans. This included addressing learning loss, supporting students' social and emotional needs, and preparing for future disruptions. – PSDS

Empathy

It is learned by the school leaders through being humble and understanding, being friendly, being empathetic, prioritizing well-being, and being a support system. This is shared by School Heads A, B, F, G, and I, who share:

“In my journey as a leader, mas nagiging humble ka. Kasi mas naiintindihan mo yung mga tao [You must be humble. You have to understand people].don't expect that you will be understood. But expect that part of your leadership that you have to be understanding.” - School Head A

“be open-minded. You have to be ready for the changes that are happening. You need to have a support system... you need to be friendly. You need to know that you have a team.”- School Head B

“empathy in leadership...Prioritizing the well-being of the school community.” -School Head F

“By prioritizing resilience, well-being, effective communication..”- School Head G

“Embracing technology as a tool for enhancing learning and communication will also remain a priority.” - School Head I

It is supported by the school division superintendent, who said:

“Strong leadership and team-building skills were essential. School heads had to inspire and motivate their staff, fostering a sense of unity and purpose despite the challenges.” – PSDS

Technological Proficiency

The most important learning that the pandemic brought to schools. Because of the forced closure of the schools and the adaptation of distance learning, school heads learned how to be technologically proficient. They learn how to upgrade themselves technologically, embrace technology as part of their tasks, use technology for effective communication, and most importantly, integrate technology into their supervision. These are shared by School Heads D, F, G, and I, who utter:

“Alam mo ang malaking natutunan ko dyan dapat ang principal magaling ka rin sa computer. Kasi kung hindi ka marunong sa computer mapag iwanan ka... kailangan i-upgrade ko rin yung sarili ko pertaining to technology.[You know what, I learned that as a principal I needed to be proficient in computer. If I am not into it (computer), I will be left behind. I have to upgrade myself toward technology].” -School Head D

“Embracing technology for effective communication and collaboration will persist.” - School Head F

“effective communication, technology integration, community-building, and distributed leadership, I am confident in my ability to lead my institution through future challenges and uncertainties..”-School Head G

“Embracing technology as a tool for enhancing learning and communication will also remain a priority.” - School Head I

This is supported by the claim of the school division superintendent who shares:

“Transitioning to online learning platforms posed significant technological challenges. School heads had to ensure that both teachers and students had access to necessary resources and training to facilitate effective online education.”-PSDS

From the three initial codes, the researcher has assigned the theme “transforming into resilient leaders” to describe the lessons learned from the experiences of school heads in leading the school during the pandemic and what they have become after their experiences.

Summary of Initial Codes and Themes

Table 1 Summary of Initial Codes and Themes

Matrix Title	Initial Code	Theme
Changes in the Leadership Roles of School Heads During the Pandemic	Situational Leadership	The school head as a situational leader during the pandemic
	Remote Leadership	
	Supporting and Motivating Team	
Changes in the Leadership Roles of School Heads After the Pandemic	Adaptive Leader	The school head as an adaptive leader after the pandemic
	Technologically Driven Leader	
	Emphatic Leader	
Perspectives of School Heads Regarding the Alterations in their Leadership Roles as the Pandemic Unfolded	Adaptation to technology, communication, and, modalities	The school heads' adaptation to technology, communication, and new modalities
	New school set-up	
	Alterations of ways to supervise	
	Adaptation to new nature of work	
	Setting of new mindset and leadership style	
Challenges that the School Heads Encountered in their Leadership Roles During the Pandemic	Unclear communication channels	The school heads' challenges in learning and assessment
	Public Health restrictions	
	Challenges in learning and assessment result reliability	

	Mental health and morale	
Subsequent Changes that the School Heads Experienced in their Leadership Roles After Confronting the Challenges	Resiliency and proactivity	The school heads' open-mindedness and commitment
	Adaptive and flexible	
	Open and committed	
Lessons Learned from the Experiences of School Heads in Leading Schools During the Pandemic	Resiliency	The school heads transformation into resilient leaders
	Empathy	
	Technological Proficiency	

DISCUSSION

Changes in the leadership roles of school heads during and after the pandemic

Khattak et al. (2023) claimed that situational leadership is valued by teachers as it enables the school heads to adapt to the demands of the circumstances. The ability of the leader to adapt to given circumstances is the most crucial part during the pandemic, as it affects both internal and external factors in school and the community. Technology, distance learning plays a significant role in linking the school, the students, and the parents (Khatoun & Daffalla, 2023).

Situational leadership during the pandemic, as employed by the school heads, helps aid services to address the health crisis and continuously provide education using technology (Pedroso et al., 2021). The ability of school heads to adapt to changing situations makes schools function as they should. The implementation of emergency plans and remote learning, combined with rapid decision-making, tests the leadership styles of the school heads and proves how flexible they were when the pandemic struck.

The changes in the leadership roles and practices of school heads after the pandemic. Based on the interview extracts, the following three initial codes are generated: adaptive leader, technologically driven leader, and empathic leader. Being adaptive is positively related to a positive attitude toward change. Specifically, it is the strongest predictor of the principal's attitude toward progress (Nedzinskaite-Maciuniene et al., 2023).

Technology in schools is an educational tool to help students in learning (Uğur & Koç, 2019, as cited in Richardson, 2022). In addition, leaders who implemented leadership practices through IT had positive student outcomes (Richardson, 2022). However, there was a study on the perceptions of the principals toward technology integration into their

jobs. Ngozwana (2025) found that their perceptions also varied by their sex and years of experience. Further, they suggested a lot of funding for leadership advancement in technology leadership to adapt to the changing modes of learning and supervision (Ngozwana, 2025).

Being an empathic leader is cited as a favorable disposition (Coppess, 2022). Empathy is a skill for leadership, pointing to the emotional intelligence (EQ) of school heads to understand and support their teachers and bring out the best in them (Taylor & Lambert, 2022). In this case, the school heads use an empathetic approach to reach out to their teachers so they can help them transition from pandemic to post-pandemic.

Being an adaptive leader means a willingness to handle situations and challenges for development and solutions (Mallillin, 2022). Moreover, it entangles creativity and innovation and attempts to design leadership mechanisms and boundaries (Patel & Lasley, 2021). Moreover, according to the Adaptive Theory Approach in Leadership, a leader must foster change by prioritizing the core values, aspirations, and capabilities of educators. Leaders invest in proactive strategies, seeking opportunities for innovation and improvement in educational practices. Thus, this inspires them to be motivated and enthusiastic to drive schools toward shared goals and partnerships by all stakeholders built on mutual trust and development.

Perspectives of school heads regarding the Alterations in their leadership roles as the pandemic unfolded

The adaptation of technology and new modalities leads teachers and school leaders to discover more about their capabilities, especially in using technology in class and supervision. Advanced technology offers immersive learning opportunities, yet it is significantly costly as different tools and equipment pose funding challenges. However, maximizing the benefits of technology equips educators with the necessary expertise useful in times of hurdles in education practice (Zhang & Wasie, 2023).

The online and modular modalities also pose challenges to the school heads, as they are dealing with teachers who prepared for modular and teachers who taught online. Several issues are also raised, not only the instructional supervision but also the students' accountability in learning. While online gadgets and offline use modules of answer sheets, the technical aspects like fluctuating internet connection or the delivery of modules and parents' unwillingness to assist their children were also big concerns (Panol et al., 2022). The changes, like work by the school heads, delve into their acceptance that they need to embrace the new approaches and modalities. They cannot do it when they are not open to changing their mindset. According to Gonzales et al. (2022), principals must note how hard it was to take in the modifications that happened during the changes; however, they are known to have a structured form of communication with technology, and this is important to get into the digital world.

According to Olayvar (2021), the leadership of school heads brings a significant collaborative culture, which is implied by sound decision-making, planning, adaptability, and collegial relationships with teachers and other stakeholders. The need for adaptive

educational leaders is increasing along with the various demands experienced by schools. In addition, adaptive leadership is needed to respond to unpredictable realities and ensure a better quality of education. In this study, the leaders are exemplified as having adaptive leadership, especially in technology, new means of communication and learning, and supervision modalities. Despite the challenges faced, the school heads still manage to address them (Fitriani, 2023).

Challenges that the school heads encountered in their leadership roles during the pandemic

Effective leadership requires excellent communication skills with students, teachers, and parents who have different expectations in the educational system; hence, fulfilling those depends on the leaders' communication skills (Salamondra, 2021).

The problem with the internet speed in the Philippines posed a great test to students and teachers during the pandemic. Asio et al. (2021) found that during the pandemic, 70% of the learners had internet access at home, while most of them used smartphones as a learning device. However, internet connectivity among these students hindered their learning (Asio et al., 2021). In this study, even communication was affected by this scenario. To add to that, the school principals had limited experience in crisis management (Lien et al., 2022), which added to the adversaries they had faced.

According to Lien et al. (2023), principals are already aware of daily minor cases, hassles, and frustrations among students, parents, and even teachers. But with COVID-19, everything was different as principals had to deal with the unknown. This leads to the fourth code, which is about mental health.

The World Health Organization (2022) has reported key findings regarding the evidence of the pandemic's impact on mental health during COVID-19. There was (1) a significant increase in mental health problems; (2) younger, female, and pre-existing health conditions were reported with risk factors; and (3) further research on mental health and COVID-19 at-risk populations was needed. Even the school heads were not exempt from the effects of mental health issues.

In response to the prevalence of Mental Health issues, the Department of Education, through DepEd. Memo 93, s. 2022 launched the National Mental Health Month, which promoted mental health in physical and virtual spaces, on October 10, 2022. It aimed to incorporate this activity into Guidance Programs at each school.

As instructional leaders, the school heads were responsible for the students' achievement. However, given the situation where the students' answers on modules and their presence in the online meeting rooms did not ensure that learning was taking place. Hence, school leaders still made sure that the deliverables were given to students by the teachers, and that support, no matter how difficult the situation, was given to them. Meanwhile, according to Snejana and Veselina (2022), the assessment of knowledge is the most difficult task for teachers amid social isolation during the COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, the teachers' collaboration on assessment is sporadic, and the routines are

weak. This has raised concerns about equity in education as teachers had problems implementing assessments that support learning (Sanvik et al., 2022).

Subsequent changes that the school heads experienced in their leadership approaches after confronting the challenges brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic

Onan et al. (2025) claim that resiliency has a highly positive relationship with leadership effectiveness. The school head shows how their experiences shaped them into a resilient and proactive leader, as they can deal with unknown situations with acceptance and openness. An adaptive and flexible principal is a leader who responds to conditions appropriately and quickly. Moreover, it is not only responding to challenges but also to problems that cannot be foreseen (Fitriani, 2023). In this study, the school heads have expressed the importance of being adaptive and flexible, which is why they survived the pandemic challenges.

The school heads have recognized themselves as open-minded and committed after the COVID-19 experiences. Thanh and Van Quang (2022) claim that leadership styles are closely related to the employees' commitment. Needless to say, if the school head is committed, that is also the case with the teachers he supervised. Moreover, there should be a skilled leader who is competent in influencing employees to aim for optimum organizational results and outcomes (Nikolic, 2022). Hence, despite the challenges faced by school leaders and teachers during the pandemic, they were able to surpass them together through open-mindedness and commitment.

Lessons learned from the experiences of school heads in leading schools during the pandemic

Rume and Islam (2020) claimed that the pandemic reminded the world that life could be too short to waste. And one should exercise responsible leadership by being resilient to contribute to a better world post-COVID-19. Being emphatic enhances leadership effectiveness (Zivkovic, 2022). Moreover, it contributes to raising awareness, listening and mentoring, enhancing relationships, empowering, providing role models, developing emotional intelligence, and enhancing organizational effectiveness (Zivkovic, 2022). The school heads learned to be empathic as they also felt how the teachers, students, and parents felt- they experienced the same challenges. The only thing that the school leaders were leading to was that they had to have more empathy to extend to others, leading them to be inspired, motivated, and united.

The role of technology is crucial as it becomes the bloodline for the continuation of limited movements caused by health restrictions. School leaders must also be adept at technology so that they can help and assist the teachers. Not only that, technology serves as a tool for communication between teachers and students, students and teachers, teachers and school heads, teachers and parents, and parents and school heads.

Resiliency should not only be present in leaders but also in employees (Mishra et al., 2023). It refers to the ability of an individual to bounce back, adapt to changes, and thrive

under pressure. Being in an uncertain situation just as COVID-19 made each one feel, the resiliency of the school heads has contributed to the existence of the schools until today. Without their leadership and connection to other stakeholders, there could be downfalls that would lead to misunderstandings and, worse, closures of schools. The pandemic has brought parents into a low socio-economic situation, which has made them unable to afford to send their students to school (Sultana et al., 2022). Even though this case could not apply to public schools where this study was made, the absence of resilience in school leaders still affected the schools' mechanisms and agility to perform at their best (Taseer & Ahmed, 2022).

Summary of Initial Codes and Themes

The first theme, "The school head as a situational leader during the pandemic," states that school heads employ situational leadership strategies that facilitate crucial services to face the health crisis brought on by the COVID-19 Pandemic and to maintain the learning process. Despite the limitations, especially in communication, the school heads have demonstrated remote supervision and maximized the online tools to ensure the engagement of students and teachers. The school heads' adaptability enables schools to operate amidst crisis, showing leadership styles under pressure and highlighting their flexibility as they respond to every adversity that comes their way.

The second theme, "The school head as an adaptive leader after the pandemic", encapsulates the transformative leadership roles and practices of the school heads during the post-pandemic. The school heads have acknowledged improvements in their leadership skills, and emotionally restructured as they improved in efficacy. Drawing from the Adaptive Theory in Leadership, the school heads have prioritized the teachers' values, capabilities, and aspirations, fostering a proactive strategy for innovation. This has energized the school heads to drive schools collaboratively with other stakeholders toward shared goals that entail trust and development among them.

The third theme, "The school heads' adaptation to technology, communication, and new modalities," illustrates how the school leaders perceived the changes in their leadership roles during the pandemic. The school heads have demonstrated adaptive leadership, especially in using technology, new communication channels, and different learning modalities. Even though the transition of modalities posed hurdles to the schools, the school heads can ensure that both teachers and students have access to available resources for teaching and learning. It is also seen that the school heads remained committed to ensuring the availability of resources and support. These have underscored the proactive response of the school heads to the difficult situation.

The fourth theme, "The school heads' challenges in learning and assessment," encompasses the difficulties faced by the school leaders in their roles during the pandemic. As instructional leaders, they have borne responsibility for student successes but were faced with uncertainties about whether this "learning" had taken place or not. Despite this, the school leaders have ensured that the teachers were still delivering teaching-learning, and they were provided with support. Another challenge is the student assessment's reliability as educational routines are weakened, which has raised concerns

about reliable educational outcomes. This highlights the obstacles the school heads encountered in navigating learning and assessment and underscores the importance of adaptive leadership and support for teachers and students.

The fifth theme, “The school heads’ open-mindedness and commitment”, shows the transformative changes school administrators experienced in their leadership practices following the pandemic. It is emphasized that leadership styles influence employees’ commitment; thus, when the school head demonstrates commitment, it will resonate with the teachers. Despite the formidable challenges encountered, the collective resilience was evident through the openness to new ideas and their steadfast commitment. This mindset and dedication enabled the school heads to navigate and overcome challenges, promoting a supportive educational environment post-pandemic.

The sixth theme, “The school heads’ transformation into resilient leaders,” reflects the profound lessons learned from school heads’ experiences in managing schools amidst the pandemic. It has underscored resilience, which was crucial not only for the school heads but also for the teachers. The uncertainty imposed by the pandemic highlighted the resilience of the school heads, which became an intrinsic part of sustaining schools through turbulent times. While families faced economic hardships, impacting the attendance of students, the school heads’ leadership affected the schools’ ability to perform. Despite these challenges, they were able to continue functioning, demonstrating their essential role in maintaining educational stability amidst the pandemic.

The lived experiences of school heads leading the school during disruptive times in response to the inquiries presented by the researcher. The changes in the leadership roles and practices of school heads during the pandemic reveal that the school had a situational leader, and certain changes and adaptations were considered to pursue its goal of providing education to the learners. Furthermore, the school head turned into an adaptive leader after the pandemic. As a flexible leader, the perspectives regarding the alterations in their leadership roles were unfolded through the adaptation of technology, communication, and new modalities.

Aside from that, the challenges that the school heads encountered in terms of their leadership roles were the modification of learning and assessment of learners. Another thing was the subsequent change that school heads experienced that tested their leadership roles. This resulted in confronting and surmounting the challenges through the manifestation of open-mindedness and commitment. Hence, several lessons were acquired in these sudden deviations caused by the pandemic, and it upheld the virtue of resilience.

Aside from this, the school heads were able to communicate even without physical presence using gadgets like mobile phones, laptops, and with internet for connection. To complete, despite hurdles experienced by the school heads, they were able to execute flexibility, became accustomed to the changes using ICT, and manifested that learning should continue even when in crisis.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were made:

1. During the pandemic, school heads turned into situational leaders, and after the pandemic, they became adaptive leaders who can adapt to whatever changes may happen.
2. The school heads perceived that the changes in their leadership roles led them to be more adaptive to technology and different modalities of communication.
3. The challenge that the school heads encountered in their leadership roles during the pandemic was about learning and assessment.
4. With subsequent changes that the school heads experienced in their leadership approaches and practices after being confronted and surmounted by the challenges brought by the COVID-19 pandemic, school heads became open-minded to changes and more committed to performing their duties despite the changes.
5. The school heads transformed into resilient leaders. Resiliency is a lesson that they have learned in leading the schools during the pandemic.

Recommendations

In light of the findings of the study, the following were recommended:

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1. The Department of Education - Division Office may develop and implement a Leadership Enhancement Program that focuses on empowering the school heads. The program may focus on topics such as situational leadership, motivating and leading the team in different situations, managing oneself, managing a team, and managing the school in different situations.
 2. While the Department of Education may conduct workshops and seminars to help the school heads learn and maximize the use of Information and Communication Technology in managing and supervising the school and the administrative and teaching staff, it is also recommended that Teacher Education Institutions offering education management programs in the graduate studies to include the same either as a separate course or an integral part of a course. School administrators may also forge linkages to the industry for training and any form of assistance that may assist the school heads in maximizing the use of ICT in their leadership.
 3. The school head may utilize the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) session to converse and share different teaching strategies and to come up with an

assessment matrix to properly align the content standards, learning competencies, and classroom activities and evaluations.

4. The Department of Education may conduct a leadership assessment involving the school heads, their subordinates, and other stakeholders to determine how to improve the leadership of the school heads.
5. Future researchers may investigate further the complexity of leadership roles during the post-pandemic period, the impact of external and internal factors that influenced leadership styles, longitudinal studies, and comparative analysis of leaders from private and public schools, and explore additional factors that could contribute to an in-depth understanding of what shapes an effective school leader. This could help inform authorities on developing policies, programs, and support systems to enhance the capacity of school heads and to help them function even in challenging times of uncertainty.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

After passing the proposal defense, the researcher submitted a letter addressed to the University Board of Ethics in Research and other relevant offices. After this, she submitted the required documents to the Research Management Office, where her ethics clearance was issued.

The researcher went to the school heads and sought their consent for individual interviews. Participants were included because of their willingness; hence, informed consent was signed by the participants. The participants were interviewed at their most convenient time, place, and manner (face-to-face or online platform) where they freely shared their information. The participant's name did not appear in the transcription of the recorded interviews, as indicated in the permission forms. The researcher adheres to the Philippine Data Privacy Act of 2012 to guarantee that the data she acquired for this study is confidential. The researcher continued the interview, outlined the study's objectives, and asked important questions.

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